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Report on the estimation of the temperature difference between the silver and copper fixed points

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1. Abstract

This document aims to evaluate the temperature difference between the silver fixed point and the copper fixed point by radiometric means, and to compare this difference with that calculated from the temperatures assigned to these two fixed points in the ITS-90. Four national metrology institutes participated in the evaluation of this difference: CMI (Czech Republic), SMU (Slovakia), RISE (Sweden), and LNE-Cnam (France).

The measurement method consists of determining the temperature T_{90} of silver cells by extrapolation in the ITS-90 from the copper point chosen as the reference, each laboratory having provided at least one silver cell and one copper cell. The main characteristics of the cells, the instruments, and experimental setups specific to each laboratory were compiled and detailed.

However, the estimates of the temperature differences between the silver point and the copper point are not sufficiently reproducible to be published. The differences between $T_{90}(Ag) - T(Ag)$ range from -127 mK to $+64$ mK, whereas the literature suggests a value closer to $+40$ mK. In some cases, the uncertainties reported by the laboratories justify these differences, but in such cases, the required level is too large to be considered acceptable. The publication of these results requires further in-depth work, particularly the harmonisation of uncertainty budgets.

2. Introduction

Above the freezing point of silver, temperature is defined in the ITS-90 by extrapolation from a reference temperature assigned to the freezing point of silver $T_{90}(Ag) = 1234,93$ K, gold $T_{90}(Au) = 1337,33$ K, or copper $T_{90}(Cu) = 1357,77$ K. The extrapolation is performed using a pyrometer through the ratio of spectral radiance measured at the reference point and at the unknown point, according to Planck's law [1].

The copper point is generally preferred to the gold point for budgetary reasons. It is also preferred to the silver point, whose radiance flux, approximately five times lower, generates a significantly noisier response. Nevertheless, the silver point remains essential because it defines the boundary between contact thermometry and radiation thermometry.

The non-uniqueness of the reference fixed points significantly degrades extrapolation toward high temperatures because the thermodynamic temperatures assigned to these ITS-90 fixed points differ from their exact thermodynamic temperatures. The difference between $[T(Cu) - T(Ag)]$ and $[T_{90}(Cu) - T_{90}(Ag)]$, of the order of 40 mK [2], generates a bias between T and T_{90} of approximately 100 mK at 3000 K. It is therefore essential to determine this difference as accurately as possible in order, first, to identify temperature discrepancies between the two scales and, second, to consider a possible revision of the thermodynamic temperatures assigned to these ITS-90 fixed points.

The purpose of this report is to evaluate the ratio of spectral radiance measured at the copper and silver points and to compare it with the ratio of spectral radiance at $T_{90}(Cu)$ and $T_{90}(Ag)$, in order to deduce the temperature difference between $[T_{90}(Cu) - T(Ag)]$ and $[T_{90}(Cu) - T_{90}(Ag)]$. Final results will be expressed as the difference $T_{90}(Ag) - T(Ag)$.

3. Measurement Principle

Measurements were independently carried out in the following four laboratories: UL, SMU, RISE, and LNE-Cnam, the respective National Metrology Institutes of Slovenia, Slovakia, Sweden, and France. Each laboratory aims to evaluate the ratio of spectral radiance at the freezing points of silver, $L_{\lambda}[T(Ag)]$, and copper, $L_{\lambda}[T_{90}(Cu)]$, in order to determine the temperature $T(Ag)$ by extrapolation from the temperature $T_{90}(Cu)$ defined in the ITS-90. It is important to note the distinction between $T(Ag)$ and $T_{90}(Ag)$: the former is calculated in this paper by extrapolation from $T_{90}(Cu)$, whereas the latter is defined in the ITS-90 as $T_{90}(Ag) = 1234,93$ K.

$T(Ag)$ is calculated from Equation 1, in which the ratio of spectral radiance at the two considered points is equal to the ratio derived from Planck's law. $c_2 = hc/k$ is the second radiation constant, where h , c , and k are the Planck constant, the speed of light in vacuum, and the Boltzmann constant, respectively.

$$\frac{L_{\lambda}[T_{90}(Cu)]}{L_{\lambda}[T(Ag)]} = \frac{\exp [c_2(\lambda T_{90}(Ag))^{-1}] - 1}{\exp [c_2(\lambda T_{90}(Cu))^{-1}] - 1} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Solving Equation 1 consists in determining $T(Ag)$ by replacing the ratio of spectral radiance $L_{\lambda}[T(Ag)]$ and $L_{\lambda}[T_{90}(Cu)]$ with the ratio of the instrument responses $R[T_{90}(Cu)]$ and $R[T(Ag)]$, respectively (Equation 2).

$$\frac{L_{\lambda}[T_{90}(Cu)]}{L_{\lambda}[T(Ag)]} \approx \frac{R[T_{90}(Cu)]}{R[T(Ag)]} \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

Since the full widths at half maximum of the slit scattering function of the instruments considered in this paper are of the order of 8 to 10 nm, the instrument responses can be linearised as follows:

$$\frac{L[\lambda_{eff}, T_{90}(Cu)]}{L[\lambda_{eff}, T(Ag)]} \approx \frac{R[\lambda_{eff}, T_{90}(Cu)]}{R[\lambda_{eff}, T(Ag)]} \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

where λ_{eff} is the effective wavelength, defined as the wavelength for which the ratio of the pyrometer responses equals the ratio of the spectral radiance being measured, with $S(\lambda)$ representing the slit scattering function of the instrument.

$$\lambda_{eff} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad \text{Eq.4}$$

The approximation associated with the effective wavelength generates an uncertainty on $T(Ag)$ smaller than 1 mK.

4. Description of the instrumentation

Table 1 shows the main characteristics of the instruments used in each laboratory. The effective wavelengths λ_{eff} were calculated from the slit scattering function $S(\lambda)$ following Equation 4, except for RISE, whose direct temperature difference was estimated from the responses of the calibrated radiation thermometer. Table 2 shows the main characteristics of the furnaces and the fixed points used in each laboratory.

The metal purity values correspond to those specified by the supplier at the time of sale, except for LNE-Cnam cells, for which the purity was measured by Glow Discharge Mass Spectrometry (GDMS) on samples taken directly from the ingot after the filling of the cells.

All cavities are cylindrical in shape with a 120° conical apex at the bottom, except for the CMI cells, which are distinguished by a cylindrical flat-bottom design whose surfaces are threaded.

Table 1: Characteristics of the radiation thermometers used for the comparison

	SMU	CMI	RISE	LNE-Cnam
Instrument used for extrapolation	Chino IR-RST65H	KE LP5	KE LP5	Radiance comparator
Spectral filter	Interferential filter	Interferential filter	Interferential filter	Monochromator
Effective wavelength λ_{eff} /nm	651,051	649,195	x	808,000
Viewing distance /cm	70	80	80	100
Target field stop diameter /mm	1	1	1	2

Table 2: Characteristics of the furnaces and the fixed points used for the comparison

	SMU	CMI	RISE	LNE-Cnam
Furnace type	Isotech Oberon R426 Na heatpipe	Isotech 17702 S Na heatpipe	Entech ETF 50/18-III 3 zones	Cerhec 3 zones
Crucible design	LNE-Cnam Hybrid design [3]	Isotech	LNE-Cnam Hybrid design	LNE-Cnam Hybrid design
Outer length x diameter /mm	44 x 24	114 x 43	44 x 24	72 x 32
Fixed point filling	SMU	Isotech	RISE	LNE-Cnam
Metal supplier Ag - Cu	Safina - American Elements	No data	Merck Life Science	Thermo Fisher Scientific - Nippon Mining and metals
Cell ID	Ag1 - Cu2	Isotech Oberon R	Ag - Cu1 - Cu2	AgM8 - CuM5
Metal purity	5N - 4N	No data	5N - 6N8 - 6N8	5N6 - 6N5
Ingot mass /g	33 28	620 480	33 - 28 - 29	134 - 113
Cavity opening diameter x inner diameter x length /mm	3 x 5 x 33	9 x 9 x 90	3 x 5 x 33	4 x 6 x 60
Cavity emissivity	0,9997	0,9999	0,9997	0,9999

Temperature setpoint	$T_{freeze} - 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$T_{freeze} - 12\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$T_{freeze} - 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$T_{freeze} - 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
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5. Apparatus, measurement procedures and specific features of the laboratories

The responses of the instruments measuring the quantities $R[T(\text{Ag})]$ and $R[T_{90}(\text{Cu})]$, defined in Equation 2, correspond to the average of the measurements taken over a minimum duration equal to one quarter of the plateau duration. When two freezing plateaus were measured on the same day, the average of the two plateaus was considered.

SMU used a single-zone furnace with temperature uniformity ensured by a sodium heat pipe. The cells originally supplied by the manufacturer were replaced by cells constructed during the Joint Research Project MultiFixRad [4, 5]. One silver cell and one copper cell were measured alternately in the furnace. The silver cell was measured on 16 and 17 March 2026, while the copper cell was measured on 19 and 24 March 2026. One or two freezing plateaus were measured each day. The pyrometer responses $R[T(\text{Ag})]$ and $R[T(\text{Cu})]$ were obtained from the average of the measurements, respectively at the silver and at the copper point over the two days (Table 3).

CMI used a single-zone furnace manufactured by Isotech, with temperature uniformity ensured by a sodium heat pipe. One silver cell and one copper cell were also supplied by the same manufacturer. Figure 2 shows a cross-section view of the cells.

Figure 2: Cross-section of the cells used by CMI. The cavity surface is fully threaded in order to increase the number of reflections and thereby improve the overall emissivity.

A total of four freezing plateaus, two at the silver point and two at the copper point were measured respectively on 15 April 2026 and 8 April 2026. The pyrometer responses $R[T(\text{Ag})]$ and $R[T(\text{Cu})]$ were obtained from the average of the measurements, respectively at the silver and at the copper point over the two days (Table 3)

RISE used a 3-zone furnace. The temperature uniformity is controlled by adjusting the 3 zones independently. The cell is placed inside graphite blocks inserted between insulating disks in order to homogenise the temperature profile. Argon is injected both from the front and the rear of the alumina tube. One silver cell and two copper cells, Cu1 and Cu2 were measured alternately in the furnace. A first comparison Ag/Cu1 was carried out in November 2024, with the cells measured in the furnace seven days apart. A second comparison, Ag/Cu2, was performed in March 2026 with a one-day interval between measurements. Finally, a third comparison $\text{Ag}/R[T_{90}(\text{Cu})]/R[T(\text{Ag})]$ The ratio $R[T_{90}(\text{Cu})]/R[T(\text{Ag})]$ was obtained from the average of the three comparisons (Table 3).

LNE-Cnam has two three-zone furnaces of identical design and configuration, allowing simultaneous comparison of the two cells, the freezing plateaus being initiated at the same time. The comparison was performed using a radiance comparator whose distinctive feature is that it is composed exclusively of mirrors. The spectral selection is achieved using a monochromator [6]. The selected cells AgM7 and CuM5 were issued

from a batch of seven silver cells and five copper cells used for the realisation of the ITS-90, whose temperature differences had previously been characterised [7]. These cells were selected as they showed the highest freezing plateaus and the best metal purity. The radiance comparator responses $R[T(\text{Ag})]$ and $R[T_{90}(\text{Cu})]$, as obtained from the average of the two measurements at the Copper point over the two days (Table 3).

6. Results

Table 3 gives the ratios of the instrument responses at the copper and silver points for each laboratory. From these ratios, the temperature differences between $T_{90}(\text{Cu})$ and $T(\text{Ag})$ are calculated, followed by the temperature differences $T_{90}(\text{Ag}) - T(\text{Ag})$.

The combined uncertainty at both Ag and Cu fixed points, includes the components related to the crucible (Impurities, Emissivity, Temperature drop, Plateau identification and repeatability), the extrapolation (wavelength, out of band transmittance, integration ...), the radiation thermometer (alignment, SSE, linearity, drift, gain ratio, ambient conditions and repeatability)

Table 3: Temperature difference $T_{90}(\text{Ag}) - T(\text{Ag})$ and associated uncertainties between the temperature $T_{90}(\text{Ag})$ assigned to the silver point in the ITS-90, and the temperature $T(\text{Ag})$ calculated by extrapolation from the Cu fixed point whose temperature is assigned in the ITS-90

	SMU	CMI	RISE	LNE-Cnam
$\frac{R[T_{90}(\text{Cu})]}{R[T(\text{Ag})]}$	5,04034	5,06214	x	3,73567
$T_{90}(\text{Cu}) - T(\text{Ag}) / \text{K}$	122,734	122,713	122,904	122,875
$T_{90}(\text{Ag}) - T(\text{Ag}) / \text{mK}$	- 106	- 127	+ 64	+ 35
Combined uncertainty at Cu FP ($k = 1$) /mK	51	39	21	18
Combined uncertainty at Ag FP ($k = 1$) /mK	49	34	19	15
$u[T_{90}(\text{Ag}) - T(\text{Ag})] / \text{mK}$ ($k = 1$)	71	52	29	24

7. Conclusion

The recent definition of the kelvin allows national temperature laboratories to perform the mise-en-pratique of the kelvin (MeP-K) by the means of fixed points whose temperatures have been assigned, either in the ITS-90 or in terms of thermodynamic temperature. This dual possibility, combined with the progress made by national metrology institutes in thermodynamic temperature measurements, challenges the coexistence of the two scales, since recent thermodynamic temperature measurements have not been integrated into the ITS-90, whose values have remained unchanged since 1990.

A precise evaluation of the temperature difference between the copper point and the silver point would make it possible for the two scales to coexist with low uncertainty, if it is carried out with an accuracy better than or comparable to that of the determination of $T - T_{90}$. The estimates presented in this report do not allow this difference to be confirmed with sufficient accuracy. A publication is therefore not feasible at this stage. It will become possible once the difference Ag/Cu has been confirmed with well-controlled uncertainties.